

Notes

Synthesis, Characterisation and Reactions of Tris(*o*-chlorophenoxy)-aluminium(III) with β -Diketones

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A survey of the literature reveals that very little attention has been focussed on the synthesis of substituted phenoxy derivatives of aluminium¹ as compared to the aluminium alkoxide and siloxide complexes². The structural chemistry of aluminium alkoxide/siloxide β -diketonate derivatives has been reported to be considerably complex³. In continuation of our previous work⁴, we report the synthesis and characterisation of $[\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}o)_3]_2$ (1). Reactions of 1 with β -diketones, such as acetylacetone (acacH), benzoylacetone (benzacH), ethylacetoneacetate (eaacH) and dibenzoylmethane (dbmH), have also been carried out in an attempt to obtain mixed phenoxy- β -diketonate and pure β -diketonate derivatives of aluminium(III).

Results and Discussion

The title compound $[\text{Al}(\text{OH}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}o)_3]$ (1) was air-stable high melting solid. Elemental analyses of the compound were in good agreement with the proposed formula. The compound was insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in nitrobenzene, acetone, acetonitrile and dichloromethane. Molar conductance value of millimolar solution of the compound in nitrobenzene suggested its non-ionic nature. Cryoscopic molecular weight determination of the compound in nitrobenzene indicated it to be dimer.

Ir spectra of the compound exhibited the general

features of the phenoxide formation as were observed in the previous reports⁴. The absence of band due to ν_{OH} mode, a significant lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ mode and appearance of bands at 585 and 570 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$ mode were the supporting evidences of compound formation. The compound appeared to be polymeric with bridging aryloxy group due to the presence of significant bands in the region 530–540 cm^{-1} which could be attributed

to $\text{Al} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \end{array} \text{Al}$ mode. The absence of any band at 480–490 cm^{-1} (Al–Cl) indicated the complete removal of chlorine on compound formation.

On the basis of ir spectral studies and cryoscopic molecular weight determination of the compound, it appeared reasonable to assign dimeric structure for the compound.

Treatment of compound 1 with β -diketones (acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, ethylacetoneacetate and dibenzoylmethane) in 1 : 2 and 1 : 6 or slightly excess than this in benzene afforded the chelates of type $[\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}o)_2 (\beta\text{-diketonate})]$ and $\text{Al}(\beta\text{-diketonate})_3$.

The elemental analyses of the complexes isolated as solids (Table 1) agreed well with the proposed stoichiometry. Formation of tris(β -diketonate) derivatives of aluminium was confirmed by their melting points, which were found to be iden-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Reaction products in molar ratio	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})	
		Al	Cl	C	H		Al–O	C=O
$\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}o)_3$	— [1 : 6]	6.47 (6.59)	25.95 (26.00)	5.31 (5.27)	3.15 (2.92)	830 (409)	590	—
Acetylacetone	$\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}o)_2\text{acac}$	7.14 (7.09)	8.72 (18.63)	49.25 (49.50)	4.12 (3.88)	395 (381)	585	1 585
	$[\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3]$	8.29 (8.33)	—	55.62 (55.7)	6.44 (6.50)	—	—	—
Benzoylacetone	$\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}o)_2\text{bzac}$	5.75 (5.8)	15.05 (15.99)	59.78 (59.45)	4.01 (3.82)	461 (444)	588	1 550
	$[\text{Al}(\text{benzac})_3]$	5.18 (5.10)	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ethylacetoneacetate	$\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}o)_2\text{eaac}$	6.13 (5.88)	8.10 (8.03)	54.49 (54.60)	3.09 (3.03)	405 (395)	580	1 610
	$[\text{Al}(\text{eaac})_3]$	6.19 (6.26)	—	—	—	—	—	—
Dibenzoylmethane	$\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}o)_2\text{dbm}$	4.79 (4.85)	14.70 (14.05)	63.87 (64.15)	3.82 (3.76)	525 (505)	582	1 548
	$[\text{Al}(\text{dbm})_3]$	3.88 (3.74)	—	—	—	—	—	—

tical with those reported earlier in literature but synthesised by different routes⁶. These results, therefore, provide an extension to the available methods for the synthesis of β -diketonate derivatives of aluminium(III).

In the ir spectra of the isolated chelates of composition $[\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}-o)_2 (\beta\text{-diketonate})]$, the occurrence of carbonyl absorptions at lower frequencies than those of the free ligands, indicated that ligands are coordinated through two oxygens⁷. This was in accordance with the infrared data on complexes of these ligands. However, the ir did not display any band at $530-540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting

any bridging mode of type $\text{Al} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{Al} \end{array}$. The presence of sharp bands at $575-595\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was attributed to terminal $\nu_{\text{Al}-\text{O}}$ ⁸. It may, therefore, be inferred that dimeric structure of the parent compound was ruptured on complex formation followed by coordination of the ligand.

Based upon the results, it may be concluded that the compound 1 is a dimer and on reacting with β -diketones in different molar ratios, leads to the formation of mixed phenoxo- β -diketonate and pure β -diketonate derivatives, thus providing an alternative route to synthesise compounds of composition $\text{Al}(\beta\text{-diketonate})_3$ already reported in literature by different methods⁹.

Experimental

Anhydrous AlCl_3 (B.D.H.) was used after purifying by sublimation in an atmosphere of chlorine. *o*-Chlorophenol was purified by distillation and the fraction distilling at 163° was collected over activated molecular sieves. Fractions of acetylacetone and ethylacetoacetate distilling at 132° and 173° respectively, were stored over molecular sieves before use. Dibenzoylmethane (m.p. 79°) and benzoylacetone (m.p. 60°) were recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride. Solvents used were dried by standard methods.

The compound of composition $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}-o)_3$ was synthesised by refluxing aluminium(III) chloride and *o*-chlorophenol in 1 : 3 molar ratio in benzene

until the evolution of HCl ceased. A white solid that separated by the addition of petroleum ether to the clear solution of the reactants, was recrystallised from CH_2Cl_2 + benzene mixture. Chelate complexes of 1 were prepared by stirring and slight heating of it with two equivalents and six-fold excess of the β -diketones in benzene in separate experiments for $\sim 6\text{ h}$. The addition of petroleum ether to the clear mixture solution yielded the complexes, which were recrystallised from benzene-acetone mixture.

Aluminium in the complexes was estimated gravimetrically by oxine method as $\text{Al}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{ON})_3$ and chlorine by Volhard's method. The molecular weight was determined in nitrobenzene by cryoscopic method. Infrared spectra (nujol/KBr) were scanned on Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 spectrophotometers.

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